

Plant Health research coordination:
an international endeavour

XX International Plant Protection Congress
Healthy Plants Support Human Welfare

3rd of July 2024

Foreword

Protecting plant health will help countries meet the UN sustainable goals. Plant health challenges are truly global in nature and require significant capacities, resources and infrastructure that cannot be found within the limits of a single country. Extending the organization of research and innovation beyond national borders allows to reconcile the tension between global research challenges and research spaces that are largely nationally organized. Since 2006, the Euphresco network for phytosanitary research coordination and funding started supported phytosanitary research programme owners and programme managers to develop and take advantage of synergies amongst national research programmes and activities. The success of Euphresco as a primarily European network for phytosanitary research coordination has set the ground for discussions on the development of initiative(s) to address the needs of other regions of the world and global phytosanitary research coordination.

Recently, funding was received to adapt the structure and operations of Euphresco to better serve a wider and more diverse membership, to enhance national and regional phytosanitary research coordination and to set the foundations for global phytosanitary research coordination through fit-for-purpose activities.

Consultations of stakeholders that operate in plant health at national and regional level are being organized. The consultations will allow to collect information for the development of a global strategic research agenda, the organization of joint transnational calls on shared research priorities and the shaping of governance, structures and operations of a global network for phytosanitary research coordination.

The concurrent session will be an opportunity to showcase the recent development of Euphresco and to collaborate with the community of the International Association for the Plant Protection Sciences to identify plant health needs for the Mediterranean region.

Baldissera GIOVANI

Concurrent session agenda

Chair: Anna Maria D'Onghia, CIHEAM-Bari

11:30	Opening Plant Health research coordination: an international endeavour <i>Baldissera Giovani (EUPHRESKO III, FR)</i> Plant Health research priorities for the Mediterranean region <i>Anna Maria D'Onghia (CIHEAM-Bari, IT)</i>
11:50	Introduction on current needs and future challenges for the Mediterranean region Tools and structures for early warning and better prediction of risks <i>Monica Carvajal Yepes (CIAT, CO)</i> In situ detection and identification of pests as an opportunity to link field and laboratory activities <i>Nicola La Porta (FEM, IT)</i> Modern tools and approaches to tackle pests in the Mediterranean crop production systems <i>Nick Papadopoulos (UTH, GR)</i> How research can support policy-making: future perspectives <i>Mariangela Ciampitti (SFR-IT)</i>
12:50	Brainstorming with the audience Future challenges (disciplines and pests) <i>Facilitated by Laura Mugnai (MPU, IT)</i> How to protect plant health in the next 10 years <i>Facilitated by Dimitris Tsitsigiannis (MPU, GR)</i> Research to address future challenges and to strengthen plant protection <i>Anna Maria D'Onghia (CIHEAM-Bari, IT)</i>
13:30	How to enable global phytosanitary research coordination: models of collaboration From research to reality: CPN bridges the gap in plant health solutions <i>Daren Mueller (ISU, US)</i> The role of the Arab Society of Plant Protection in enhancing plant health research coordination in the Arab region <i>Safaa Kumari (ICARDA, LB)</i> International Association for the Plant Protection Sciences <i>Geoff Norton (UG, AU)</i>
14.00	Closing

Plant Health research coordination: an international endeavour

B. Giovani

Euphresco, 21 Bd Richard Lenoir, 75011 Paris, France

Email: bgiovani@euphresco.net

It is not possible to avoid all the challenges to plant health posed by global trade, increasing travel activities and climate change. However, it is possible to optimise strategies to address these challenges with effective coordination and cooperation. Research plays a key role in underpinning phytosanitary activities, ranging from pest risk analysis, regulation, surveillance, taxonomy, diagnostics and mitigation measures. Research also helps to maintain and develop scientific expertise and infrastructure that support plant health.

The Euphresco network for phytosanitary research coordination and funding started in 2006 to support phytosanitary research programme owners and programme managers to develop and take advantage of synergies amongst national research programmes and activities.

The success of Euphresco as a primarily European network for phytosanitary research coordination has set the ground for discussions on the development of initiative(s) to address the needs of other regions of the world and global phytosanitary research coordination.

The presentation will showcase the role of Euphresco as a platform for phytosanitary research coordination and collaboration and how the network has evolved since 2006.

Plant Health research priorities for the Mediterranean region

A.M. D'Onghia

Centre International Des Hautes Etudes Agronomiques Méditerranéennes-Bari, Via Ceglie 9,
70010 Valenzano, Italy

email: donghia@iamb.it

Mediterranean agriculture, forests and other environments are seriously threatened by numerous quarantine and emerging pests, and their negative impacts are expected to increase due to the acceleration of global trade and to climate change that respectively favour the movement of these organisms over long distances and facilitate their adaptation to new environments. To address these threats, plant health challenges require rethinking the organization and coordination of research in all countries for: reducing fragmentation of actions; converging national programs; optimizing funding; and building critical mass. In this context, the Compendium on "Plant Health Research Priorities for the Mediterranean Region", published in 2021 to celebrate the International Year of Plant Health, was the first joint initiative of Euphresco and CIHEAM Bari launched to improve the coordination of research on plant health in the Mediterranean region and to enhance stakeholder cooperation in the area. The compendium reports the information and views from national experts from the Balkan-Mediterranean, Eastern Mediterranean, Maghreb, and Western Mediterranean sub-regions on priorities of pests, research, infrastructures and capacity. The Compendium was updated in 2022 with a Supplement containing research needs for priority pests of common interest to the Mediterranean countries, which should be addressed in the short-term. Among these priorities, the following topics were selected for the Euphresco round of transnational collaboration: 1. Epidemiological studies on the potential vectors of *Xylella fastidiosa*; 2. Validation of DNA extraction from different matrices/hosts of *X. fastidiosa*; 3. Development/validation of diagnostic tests to identify exotic/severe strains of citrus tristeza virus (CTV); 4. Research topic on tomato brown rugose fruit virus (TBRFV). The Mediterranean model will inspire the consultations that will be conducted in Euphresco III project on a global scale to gather information useful for developing the strategic research agenda and identifying topics of common interest for transnational collaboration.

Tools and structures for early warning and better prediction of risks

M. Carvajal-Yepes

The Alliance of Bioversity International & the International Center for Tropical Agriculture,
Palmira, Colombia

Email: m.carvajal@cgiar.org

Early warning systems involves the timely detection and communication of potential or emerging threats posed by pests and diseases. This can be achieved through the use of various tools developed in the last decades. For instance, incorporating molecular analysis aids in identifying pathogens at a genetic level, in order to understand their potential impact. Satellite imagery, drones and other remote sensing technologies enable high-resolution data collection for monitoring crop health and detecting early signs of diseases. Furthermore, data analytics and machine learning are deployed to predict pest and disease outbreaks. While tools are crucial, the structures facilitating collaborations for sharing information, capacity and coordinating efforts in disease monitoring and management, are equally or more important. In this talk, we will review examples of tools, structures, and the role of the CGIAR centers in facilitating the identification of potential signs of pest and disease outbreaks at an early stage. This allows for prompt and target intervention to mitigate or prevent significant damage to crops.

***In situ* detection and identification of pests as an opportunity to link field and laboratory activity**

N. La Porta

Fondazione Edmund Mach, Via Mach 1, 38098 San Michele all'Adige, Italy

Email: nicola.laporta@fmach.it

Early detection of plant diseases is a crucial factor to prevent or limit the spread of a pest that could cause significant economic loss. Testing in the laboratory can be laborious, time consuming, expensive, and usually requires specific technical expertise. Moreover, in developing countries, it is often difficult to find laboratories equipped for this kind of analysis. Therefore, in the past years, efforts have been made for the development of fast, specific, sensitive, and cost-effective tests that can be successfully used directly in the field by non-expert personnel using simple equipment. Nucleic acid-based methods have proven to be a good choice for the development of detection tools in several sectors, such as human/animal health, food safety, and water analysis, and their application in plant pathogen detection is becoming more and more common. The portable laboratory features inexpensive instruments that can be carried as hand luggage and uses standard molecular biology methods, protocols and reagents that tolerate adverse environmental conditions. *In situ* diagnostic methods have a high potential for early detection of pests for agriculture and forestry, as they allow molecular detection of plant pests accessible to anyone, anywhere, and at any time. *In situ* methods should not replace laboratory testing, which remains essential for activities such as identification and classification of new pests or for the study of plant defence mechanisms. Instead, these new methods can provide a useful, fast, and efficient preliminary *in situ* screening that can strengthen our approach against plant pest.

Modern tools and approaches to tackle pests in the Mediterranean crop production systems

N.T. Papadopoulos

University of Thessaly, Fytokou Str., 384 46 Nea Ionia, Volos, Greece

Email: nikopap@uth.gr

Laying on three continents, the coastal Mediterranean areas and countries in general, constitute a unique social, physical and agricultural environment. Same or similar crops are cultivated, and often identical pest problems are encountered. Several alien invasive species arrive first in the Mediterranean countries towards invading Europe. In addition, climate change has already a dramatic impact on crop production and management of pests in the Mediterranean food production systems. Recent technological advances render available a range of tools, services and approaches that can be adopted for pest management purposes. These include among others, electronic sampling and pest monitoring systems (e.g. e-traps), precise mapping and interactive spatial depiction of pest populations and crop infestation rates, bioclimatic and population growth modelling, novel forecasting approaches, mapping and tracing of pest management interventions, real time sharing of large amount of data. The presentation will elaborate on management of current and imminent threats of Mediterranean crops by pests, placing special emphasis on alien invasive species. Use and adoption of modern technology to tackle these pests is discussed considering the never-ending need for high quality and precision data from the field. Examples of modern approaches to address invasive fruit flies in Europe are provided by the recently concluded and the ongoing Horizon 2020 funded projects FF-IPM and REACT respectively. A list of areas for developing common approaches and strengthening of the collaboration among plant protection agencies across Mediterranean countries will be discussed.

How research can support policy-making: future perspectives

M. Ciampitti

Servizio Fitosanitario DG Agricoltura, Piazza Città di Lombardia 1, 20124 Milano, Italy

Email: mariangela_ciampitti@regione.lombardia.it

Research can play a crucial role in supporting policy-making on plant health and plant protection.

Plant protection authorities have the task to adopt effective measures for the protection of the territory and its plants, ensure safe trade, and mitigate the impacts of climate change on the health of crops and forests; policy-makers are supposed to develop integrated decision making through scientists and economists working within an interdisciplinary framework. The World Trade Organization emphasizes that phytosanitary measures must be anchored in science, based on a risk assessment, and follow international standards, guidelines, and recommendations developed by the International Plant Protection Convention.

In this framework, collaboration between policy-makers and researchers and between the different research teams, should be promoted and encouraged, at national level, but especially at international level as quarantine and emerging plant pests move without respecting borders.

International research collaboration across nations, institutions and disciplines leads to higher quality of science, efficient use of resources, better outcomes and wider research results dissemination. However, these benefits of collaboration only occur where there is mutual interest and alignment of goals (including a “vision”), effective leadership, facilitation of processes and structures, support for collaboration, and ultimately funding – for both research and collaboration. In addition, the need to develop a balanced portfolio of research work, ranging from strategic to applied research, is essential in creating synergistic collaboration.

The IPPC community is striving to set by 2030 a voluntary mechanism for global phytosanitary research coordination, to accelerate development of science to support all regulatory phytosanitary activities. A network of organisations that fund research projects and coordinate national research in the phytosanitary area, like Euphresco, may provide useful perspectives on policy and structures for this new mechanism.

Through research coordination and a close relationship between researchers and policymakers, the competent authorities will then be able to develop more effective policies and regulations to mitigate plant pest risks and ensure sustainable food production.

From research to reality: CPN bridges the gap in plant health solutions

D. Mueller

Iowa State University, 2205 Adv Tch Res Bd, 2213 Pammel Dr, Ames, IA 50011-1101,
Unites States of America

Email: dsmuelle@iastate.edu

The Crop Protection Network (CPN) spearheads a multinational alliance, uniting university and provincial extension specialists with public and private experts. Fueled by unbiased research, the CPN empowers farmers and agricultural professionals to make informed decisions protecting alfalfa, cotton, corn, small grains, and soybeans. Beyond state and international boundaries, the CPN amplifies the reach of agricultural extension, serving as a vital conduit for research on plant health. This network actively shares impactful content, from practical guidelines to groundbreaking discoveries, equipping stakeholders with the latest tools to tackle crop protection challenges effectively. At its heart, the CPN boasts a robust network of over 300 specialists spanning 40 U.S. states and Ontario, Canada. This collaborative platform fosters interdisciplinary teamwork, forging research alliances and seamlessly sharing scientific knowledge. Grounded in rigorous research, the CPN harnesses collective expertise to tackle complex problems in plant health, ultimately driving more effective and sustainable agricultural practices.

The role of the Arab Society of Plant Protection in enhancing plant health research coordination in the Arab region

S.G. Kumari, K.M. Makkouk and I. Al-Jboory
Arab Society for Plant Protection, Beirut, Lebanon

Email: s.kumari@cgiar.org

The strategic objectives in plant health research and development in any country or region are achieved through (i) enhancement of understanding and knowledge of plant health issues and solutions, (ii) development of evidence-based risk assessment policy approaches to empower delivery partners and practitioners to make solid decisions and take necessary action, (iii) develop and adopt innovations and new technologies in support of plant health policy objectives, and (iv) create high-quality plant health research capabilities. The Arab Society for Plant Protection (ASPP), can play an influential role in achieving some of the above-mentioned objectives by enhancing collaboration among scientific groups from different Arab and Mediterranean countries through a variety of activities such as (i) organizing regional conferences that bring together scientists from different Arab countries and the rest of the world to shed light on significantly important plant health issues of common concern and publicize best pest management practices, (ii) organizing regional workshops addressing specific plant health issues that require joint effort, (iii) encourage and facilitate distribution of up-to-date knowledge related to crop health management, and (iv) enhance technical skills through specialized courses. In addition, ASPP can facilitate the formation and implementation of joint regional research projects that focus on plant health management. Furthermore, ASPP can play an essential role in identifying plant health challenges facing the Arab region and reflecting on future solutions that are needed to minimize yield losses caused by pests to enhance food security for future generations in the Arab region.

The International Association for the Plant Protection Sciences

G. Norton¹, E. A. Heinrichs, and M. Tamo

¹The University of Queensland, PO Box 5486 Stafford Heights, Brisbane, Queensland 4053, Australia

Email: g.norton@uq.edu.au

The origin of IAPPS dates back to the first International Plant Protection Congress (IPPC), held in Belgium in 1946. Subsequently, *ad hoc* committees were formed to plan future IPPCs, until the late 1990s, when IAPPS was formally established (54 years later) at the 2000 IPPC meeting in Jerusalem. IAPPS has overseen subsequent IPPCs, generally, at four-year intervals.

Currently, the IAPPS Board consists of:

- an executive committee including a President, Vice President, Secretary General, Treasurer
- fourteen International Regional coordinators, covering the major continents
- representatives that include the Association of International R&D Centres for Agriculture, the Biopesticide Industry, Elsevier Crop Protection (IAPPS official journal), and the next IPPC Chair

The mission in IAPPS – *‘to promote the development of an integrated approach to plant protection research and its practical application’* – involves the following:

- oversight of the IPPC and encouraging the information exchange that occurs
- involvement in regional seminars and workshops
- providing news items, newsletters, and online educational and training materials
- support the development of national and regional plant protection societies

Therefore, over the past two decades, IAPPS has extended its activities well beyond its involvement in the IPPC. During the years prior to Covid, this increasingly involved IAPPS members, together with participants from other agencies, organising regional seminars and workshops, largely focussed on emerging pest problems. In the past year or so, there has been a revival of these activities.

However, the major development has been the increased role of IAPPS in digital communication. For instance, IAPPS now provides:

- the popular, Global Plant Protection News blog
- the monthly IAPPS Newsletter, posted on the IAPPS website (www.plantprotection.org), and subsequently published in the hard copy of the Crop Protection Journal
- online access to Crop Protection (the official IAPPS journal) for IAPPS members
- access to up-to-date summaries of recent articles in Crop Protection

An education and training section has recently been added to the IAPPS website, managed by an IAPPS editorial committee. Digital publications include a series of plant protection ‘stories’: a multi-author review of digital identification tools for plant biosecurity; and online pathway keys for identifying insect pests and natural enemies of rice in Asia & West Africa.

Where possible, material on the IAPPS website is published both as down-loadable, pdf documents as well as online (html) publications. This has the advantage of allowing users to view the article in their local language, using the Google Translate facility embedded in the IAPPS website.

The IAPPS Board is always interested in exploring new ways in which we might work collaboratively with other agencies to achieve common goals more effectively.